

Empowering Herders: Improving Animal Health Training to Overcome Climate Change Challenges

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Sheep health care

Climate change has a significant impact on animal health by influencing the distribution and prevalence of parasitic, infectious and metabolic diseases. Changes in temperature, humidity and rainfall patterns create favourable conditions for the spread of pathogens (bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites), as well as their arthropod vectors (ticks and insects), increasing the incidence of certain diseases. Empowering shepherds with practical training adapted to the specific conditions of warmer and wetter climates will empower farmers response to mitigate these challenges. Through participatory workshops and the sharing of knowledge and accessible digital tools, shepherds can acquire practical strategies to prevent certain diseases. The most relevant aspects to be tackled, among other topics, should include vector control, parasite infection monitoring, hoof hygiene to prevent wheezing and climate-resilient grazing practices. Local and cost-effective solutions such as the selection of preventive grazing areas, improved drainage in retention areas, and programmed parasite infection control practices and vaccination plans could be promoted. Pilot programmes implemented in semi-arid regions, such as those in the Mediterranean basin, show a 40% reduction in disease-related mortality, in addition to more sustainable land use and greater awareness among shepherds of preventative measures. The shepherds involved also show greater confidence in the practices to be adopted to mitigate the effects of climate change on animal health. By reinforcing local knowledge and promoting adaptive capacity, these initiatives help to define strategic plans to protect farms from health risks, promote the rational and sustainable use of anti-parasitics, improve productivity and food safety, and strengthen animal welfare, following the One Health concept based on agroforestry grazed systems.

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